

Compliance checking for construction project data with linked data

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Abstract

The construction industry has seen an increase in digitalisation in recent years, leading to production of ever larger amounts of data. This data is often siloed in specific systems and file formats, making it hard to connect it in a holistic representation of a built asset. Existing research suggests that this gap between disparate silos could be bridged using Semantic Web Technologies (SWT). Application of SWT results in a formal and explicit knowledge representation, making it possible to ensure compliance checking of construction project data coming from different sources. While promising, scalability of SWT application in the built environment was hindered by the lack of clear modelling guidelines. Such guidelines were recently introduced to the European market in the form of a standard, EN 17632-1:2022: Building Information Modelling (BIM) – Semantic Modelling and Linking (SML), prescribing a Top Level Information Model and a set of information modelling patterns. Considering that the Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) information model and format is currently the most used exchange standard for BIM data, this dissertation will analyse and present the means of expressing both the IFC schema as well as IFC datasets according to the guidelines specified in the EN 17632 standard. For the first contribution, the SML Top Level Information Model is extended with concepts from the IFC schema. Secondly, conventional IFC datasets are converted to a Linked Data graph applying the SML-based version of the IFC schema as well as the SML information modelling patterns. In an expedition at the end of the research,

the possibilities of compliance checking over the converted IFC datasets are explored, first in theory and then in practical application in a wider context of digital building permitting process.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/ibrWxkpSiDk>

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